

Satisfaction Towards Discotheque At Raipur Chhatisgarh

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Abstract:

The objective of the study was to Customer satisfaction in Discotheque plays the important Role in Raipur Chhattisgarh, in the busy life style every young and old people are continuously facing a lot of stress other than the job, that is why the subject of Customer Satisfaction is gained attention in Raipur, the study was done assess the customer satisfaction and services of Discotheque worker and associated with different dimensional variable in customer satisfaction and services of Discotheque in Raipur. The data was collected using Customer Satisfaction Survey questionnaire & analysed using SPSS-9, level of Customer satisfaction is measure in Five-Point Likert's scale rating and Chi-Square. The result of the study showed that Most of the respondents are young and energetic and they are satisfied with Discotheque services their ambience, music and the environment. The customer mostly visited in two area like are in Disco the que Titoss and tequila.

Keywords: Customer Preference, Discothèque, Satisfaction Survey, Raipur.

1. Introduction

A discothèque is an entertaining place or club where the recorded music played by "Discaires" (Disc jockeys) through the technology named as a PA system. Discotheque does not have an on-stage band but a music system with recorded loud music. Discotheque word is derived from the French word discothèque (a type of nightclub). Previously, most bars and nightclubs used live bands as entertainment. Discotheque mainly comprises of a disco floor, bar spot, lightshow, and a stage for a person known as disc jockey where he/she plays recorded song or music. Discotheques have bouncers at the entry point and inside the theque, where they usually do not admit people with informal clothing and they look that nothing goes wrong in terms of maintaining the discipline of the discotheque. They have the power to restrict entry to the club and remove people. For legal purpose, bouncers check ID to ensure the person is of legal drinking age and that they are not intoxicated already. The busiest nights are Friday and Saturday and most of them cater to certain music genres, such as house music or hip hop. Entering a discotheque, requires a cover charge and it varies with factors such as special guests, early arrivals, married couple and so on and sometimes they get free entrance also.

2. Aim

- a. To determine if there is any significant association between the Choice of Discotheque and frequency of visits with the reasons for frequency

3. Methods

4.1 Study Design and Data Collection

A Cross sectional study using Non-Probabilistic Convenience Sampling and Random Sampling was conducted in two of the discotheques in Raipur Chhattisgarh. There are many discotheques in Raipur. Our study focused on the two mostly visited disco theques. They are: Titoss and Tequila. We have observed that with the similarity in spending patterns there is a huge difference in the number of customers visiting both the outlets and the focus of our study

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was to determine what the factors responsible for it. Cross Tabulation is used to determine the relation between two variables. In this survey we have cross tabulated with the Discotheques choice and the frequency of visit with the reasons for frequency. Chi-Square Test is used to determine if there is any significant association between the Discotheque choice, the frequency of visits with the reasons for frequency. ANNOVA Table, Descriptive Analysis is used to determine on why the customers prefer one discotheque over the other by taking the satisfaction rating factors like, dance floor, crowd behavior, ambience, service, availability of order, gender and frequency of visits. Data directly collected from targeted respondents of Raipur. Well-structured questionnaire was used as a tool. For sample design, target population was Youth and students of Raipur, Chhattisgarh. People who visit Discotheques were the Sampling Element and with 120 as the sample size. For the study, 120 questionnaires were circulated and composed over a period of one month. SPSS-9 was used to analyse the data. Necessary precautions were taken to ensure that there are no missing values. Chi-Square Tests and correlation analysis was used.

4. Results

A study sample had shown (58.3%) Males and (41.7%) Females and 48.3% of them were in 18-22 Year Age Group. People go to both Titoss and Tequila but Titoss visitors are comparatively more than Tequila and the frequency of visit to any of the discotheques is monthly (37.5%) followed by weekly (30.0%), after examination (19.2%) and daily (13.3%)

See Table -1.

Table 1. Various characteristics of respondents visiting discotheque of Raipur, Chhattisgarh.

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	70	58.3
	Female	50	41.7
Age	18-22	58	48.3
	22-25	51	42.5
	25-28	11	9.2
Preference of Discotheque	Titoss	63	52.5
	Tequila	57	47.5
Frequency of Visit to Discotheque	Daily	16	13.3
	Weekly	36	30.0
	Monthly	45	37.5
	After examination	23	19.2
Reason of Visit to Discotheque	Dance Floor	48	40.0
	Peer visit with friends	32	26.7
	Hangouts	27	22.5
	Food and drinks	9	7.5
	other factors	4	3.3
Spending's in Discotheque	Below 200	38	31.7
	200-500	61	50.8
	500-1000	17	14.2
	above 1000	4	3.3

Beverages Order	Soft drinks	12	10.0
	Hot drinks	24	20.0
	Cocktail	15	12.5
	Beer	40	33.3
	Breezer	29	24.2

Chi-Square Tests for each of the characteristics is mentioned in below table -

Pearson Chi-Square	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Choice of discotheque and age group	1.520(a)	2	.468
Choice of the discotheque and gender	8.258(b)	1	.004
Choice of the discotheque and frequency of visit	8.703(a)	3	.034
Reason of visiting and preference of discotheque	13.937(a)	4	.007
Choice of discotheque and their spending	13.908(a)	3	.003
Beverages ordered and choice of discotheque	3.906(a)	4	.419

Interpretation:

- Age group- Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that age and the choice of the discotheque are independent of each other.
- Gender - So, from this as the value is less than .1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that there is a dependency between choice of the discotheque and the gender and are dependent of each other.
- Frequency of visit – So, from this as the value is less than .1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that there is a dependency between choice of the discotheque and the frequency of visit.
- Reason of visit - Since the P value is less than 0.1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis so we conclude that there is a dependency between the choice of the discotheque and the reasons for their visit and they are dependent of each other.
- Spending pattern - We infer that the P value is less than 0.1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis we conclude that there is a dependency between the choice of the discotheque and their spending behavior and are dependent.
- Beverages ordered - From the above we infer that the value of P is more than 0.1, therefore we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis. So, we conclude that they independent and there is no association between the order that the people gave and the choice of the discotheque.

Cross Tabulations was performed to determine the relation between two variables

1. Cross tabulation for discotheques choice and the frequency of visit: From this analysis we infer that people visiting discotheque monthly and weekly are more the comparatively higher than of daily and after examination.
2. Cross tabulation for discotheques choice and the reason of visit: So, by this analysis we can infer that people visit Tequila due to the dance floor whereas in titoss people visit because of dance floor peer visiting and hangouts.

3. Cross tabulation between frequency of visits and reason behind frequency of visits: The frequencies of visits were measured on daily, weekly, monthly and after examinations basis. The reasons of frequency which we felt would be preferred by the respondents are dance floor, peer group influence, hangouts, food&drinks.

From the above data we observe that most respondents visit the Titoss on a weekly & monthly basis, followed by after examinations and seldom on a daily basis.

Most number of respondents prefer going to Titoss because of its dance floor and peer group influence.

From the above data we observe that most respondents visit Tequila on a monthly basis, followed by weekly, daily and after examinations. Most number of respondents prefers going to Tequila mostly due to dance floor followed by peer group influence other factors.

Table 2. Satisfaction level of the people towards discotheques in Raipur

Satisfaction Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Satisfaction towards dance floor	Dissatisfied	16	13.3
	Neutral	38	31.7
	Satisfied	40	33.3
	Highly Satisfied	26	21.7
Satisfaction towards service	Dissatisfied	13	10.8
	Neutral	49	40.8
	Satisfied	40	33.3
	Highly Satisfied	18	15.0
Satisfaction towards crowd behavior	Dissatisfied	6	5.0
	Neutral	45	37.5
	Satisfied	52	43.3
	Highly Satisfied	17	14.2
Satisfaction towards ambience	Dissatisfied	8	6.7
	Neutral	44	36.7
	Satisfied	44	36.7
	Highly Satisfied	24	20.0
Satisfaction towards music	Dissatisfied	0	0.0
	Neutral	41	34.2
	Satisfied	53	44.2
	Highly Satisfied	26	21.7

Interpretation: From the above we can infer that people are satisfied (33.3%) with the dance floor of the two discotheques and only few are dissatisfied (13.3%) and people's satisfaction levels are neutral (40.8%) & satisfied (33.3%) to the service provided by the discotheque and only few are dissatisfied (10.8%) with the service. From the table 2, it is clear that more people are satisfied (43.3%) with the crowd behavior of the two discotheques and only few are dissatisfied (5.0%) with the crowd behavior and also, we can infer that there is equality between the satisfaction and the neutral level (36.7%) of the people and very few people are dissatisfied (6.7%) with the ambience provided by the two discotheques and mostly satisfied (44.2%) with the music of the discotheque.

4. Discussion

Out of the two discotheques where the study was carried out, we inferred that people go to both titoss and tequila but titoss visitors (52.5%) are comparatively more than tequila (47.5%). From the study it was also found that apart from the two studied discotheques, customers seldom visit other discotheques. Most of the respondents collectively (90.8%) fall within the age group of 18-22 and 22-25 yrs of age and youth. In our study it is revealed that most of the customers visit the discotheques on a monthly basis and influence of peer groups was the major reason for visiting the discotheque. When it comes to the spending's in the discotheques, most of the customers spending falls between Rs.200-Rs.500 and there is a relation between the spending pattern per visit and the choice of the discotheque.

From the study it is made very clear that most of the customers want the discotheques to be open till late night and they usually prefer to order beers and breezer for male and female respectively rather than soft drinks. Customer visiting discotheques hardly go to there for only food.

5. Conclusion

The measurement of the Customer satisfaction in disco the ques in Raipur city will provide the good quality of service in their customer. In the study, when the relationships were made between the different variables, it was found that there is a relation between the choice of the discotheques to that of the gender and the frequency of their visits. The result shows that large number of customers attend the Disco three or more time per weekly & they like their environment. The frequency of their visit shows the positive satisfaction of the customer.

on the other hand, the services provided by the customers will also increase the Customer satisfaction level in Disco the Ques and most of the customer will satisfied with environment of the Disco. but the disco the ques of the Raipur will really need to improve their Dance Floor and Service. So that they can increases the frequency of their visits customer. and also they can motivated their staff for frontline service and give them extra training and development to increase the number of customer.

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